

Modern Solutions for Treating Nose Injuries

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Abstract: Depending on the surgical method, the following types of septoplasty are distinguished: Ultrasonic. Recommended for C-shaped curvature.

Radio wave. Surgitron corrects curvature without affecting cartilage and bone tissue.

Classic. It is characterized by removing the curvature of the bone by removing the cartilage. At the end of the process, a plate is installed that sets the desired position. Often the tip of the nose hangs. The downside is a lot of blood loss.

Key words: Chronic sinusitis, rhinitis, otitis, Occasional headache, Partial or complete loss of smell, Difficulty breathing due to nasal congestion, Snoring and apnea, Epistaxis, Visible septum deformation, narrowing of nasal passages.

Endoscopic. It can be combined with laser technique or done separately. It is used with vasotomies for medical reasons.

Reimplantation of autocaltilage is carried out with the help of an endoscope, i.e. bone is repaired by preliminary removal of cartilage and subsequent restoration.

Laser. Only cartilage is removed (septochondrocorrection) or cartilage is combined with bone. In this case, local anesthesia is used.

Today, laser and endoscopic septoplasty are actively used. A comparative description of the two procedures is as follows:

Indications and contraindications

80% of the population has a deviation of the nasal septum. However, this does not mean that surgery is necessary. The following symptoms may be a reason to contact a plastic surgeon:

Chronic sinusitis, rhinitis, otitis.

Occasional headache.

Partial or complete loss of smell.

Difficulty breathing due to nasal congestion.

Snoring and apnea.

Bleeding from the nose.

Visible deformation of the septum.

Narrowing of the nasal passages.

Restrictions for septoplasty are standard and do not differ from other types of surgery.

The progress of the operation

Septoplasty is performed as follows

The doctor separates the soft tissues in the nasal passages and cleans them.

If necessary, the cartilage is removed.

The crooked bony structures are removed and the cartilage and bone are symmetrically repositioned.

If the cartilage is resected, it will regenerate.

Sutures are made with biodegradable material.

A bactericidal tampon is placed in each nostril.

A tight bandage is applied.

Rehabilitation

The patient is under the supervision of a doctor for 2-3 days. The total recovery period after surgery lasts about three months. After this time, the result of plastic surgery can be evaluated.

The postoperative period continues as follows:

To facilitate breathing, special air tubes are installed in the nasal passages and tampons are placed to absorb the separated fluid and blood. In addition, the nose is fixed with splints, plates and bandages that keep the bone tissue and cartilage in the desired position.

It is forbidden to drink water immediately after the procedure. If the pain threshold is strong, analgesics are prescribed.

The recovery period is spent at home, but you must visit the doctor every three days. During this period, the patient needs:

Treat the mucous membrane with a saline solution several times a day. For example, Aqualor, Dolphin. They relieve swelling, help remove mucus and prevent the development of infection.

Clean the space from blood clots.

Remove the shells. You should not do this procedure with your fingers. For this purpose, cotton balls are used.

Lubricate the mucous membrane with ointments. The doctor prescribes the right tool to reduce dryness and reduce the number of cracks.

After 10 days, swelling appears, and after 5 days, the respiratory function is partially normalized.

General requirements to apply:

Rinse with cold water.

Measure body temperature three times a day. The normal value is up to 37.8 ° C.

Apply a cold compress several times a day.

Monitor the hydration of the mucous membrane.

Sleep only in a semi-sitting position, put several pillows under your head.

The main prohibitions during the rehabilitation period:

Do not use vasoconstrictor drops or sprays.

Do not eat very hot food.

Do not blow your nose or touch your nasal passages with your hands.

Do not visit the bath, solarium or other places exposed to heat.

Do not lower your head.

Do not play sports.

Do not wear glasses.

Do not sneeze with your mouth closed.

Complications

The possibility of developing some side effects after septoplasty is low. They are mainly related to non-compliance with the doctor's recommendations in the postoperative period.

Standard symptoms after nasal septum surgery are bleeding, fever and pain. In addition, swelling occurs. Its severity is noticeable in the first seven days, and then decreases for a month. To reduce the appearance of swelling, you should apply a cold compress, use vasoconstrictors and moisten the air in the room.

Among the negative events, the following should be noted:

Hematomas. It occurs due to damage to blood vessels. As a rule, it goes away by itself.

Scars of the nasal septum.

Infection due to improper treatment of the nasal passages.

Reduction or complete loss of sensitivity of the skin of the nose as a result of nerve damage.

Epithelial mucosa damage.

Dry throat and nose.

Change in the color of the epidermis.

Serious complications after surgery include:

Perforation of the nasal septum wall. It is expressed as a whistling sound when breathing.

Purulent sinusitis. It manifests itself as a sharp pain, blocked ears, dizziness and an increase in body temperature. This is due to insufficient drainage, insufficient washing of the sinuses and wound infection. Antibacterial therapy is necessary.

Inflammation of the cartilage area.

Accumulation of fluid in the nasal cavity.

Recurrent obstruction. This problem requires repeated plastic surgery.

Damage to the internal valve. This group includes difficulties such as severe narrowing of cartilage tissue, narrowing of the bony arch, narrowing of the nasal wings.

A headache, a dry throat appears and it becomes difficult to breathe. In this case, a secondary operation is required.

Fusion of the walls of the nasal cavity. Bridges make it difficult for air to pass through. Dry mouth, snoring and voice changes appear. It can be removed surgically. After the procedure, splints are placed to prevent the threads from reappearing.

Laser technology reduces the possibility of complications.

Factors that increase the occurrence of negative events are surgical procedures with existing contraindications, non-observance of sterility during processing, taking prohibitive drugs, early physical activity and low blood coagulation.

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